

Enabling intuitive smart programming in industrial processes

Gianluca Lentini¹, Francesca Negrello¹, Marc Galusi³, Giorgio Grioli¹, Stefano Ierace⁴,
Antonio Bicchi^{1,2} and Manuel G. Catalano¹

Abstract—Today robotics offers robust and sophisticated hardware solutions that are leading the market to mass production. However, the high demand for small batches of highly customized products requires flexible processes, and the considerable cost of programming robotic systems induces many companies to still rely on manual labor even for low value-added tasks. In this context, Learning from Demonstration (LfD) has established as a promising method for transferring capabilities from humans to robots. This paper proposes a programming framework that allows non-expert users to intuitively program a robotic system for a product testing task. Finally, we validated our approach in both a simulated environment and real-world use cases.

Index Terms—Learning from Demonstration, smart programming, flexible manufacturing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The capabilities of robots are gradually evolving and their presence in industrial environments is constantly increasing. Nevertheless, the programming of robots remains a crucial obstacle to their massive proliferation. An analysis of the average lifetime cost of a robotic cell [5] shows that only 25-35% of the cost is hardware, 5% is operating costs (maintenance, power supply), and 60-70% is programming. The frequent reprogramming of a robotic system arises from the need to respond quickly to an increasingly dynamic and customized market consisting of small batches. This requires flexible and easily re-programmable production and assembly lines capable of producing different products, optimizing space requirements, and increasing the payback of initial investment.

LfD has shown promise over the years as a method for transferring capabilities from humans to robots [1]. The scientific community developed various tools to demonstrate a task to a robot, as well as methods to encode and generalize the learned actions in a new situation. Although the link between perception and action has been demonstrated in several psychological and neurobiological studies, it is important to determine and select what is relevant for performing a given task. This challenge is addressed in several works, e.g. [4], where the teacher's task is to highlight the salient parts of the task, while others use a statistical approach [2], which may require a large number of demonstrations.

In this paper, we tested our previous work [3] in a real industrial application and introduced a neural network in the

Fig. 1. The smart workstation for control station testing is composed by a robotic arm, a depth-camera and a neural network.

demonstration phase that allows the robot to identify small elements that would not have been detected by the previous method. In particular, the use case concerns the testing of wired control station (Fig. 1). An intuitive framework for robot programming is proposed that allows the user to easily show the robot how to interact with the different controls on the keypad in order to complete the product test. In this way, the robot creates its own library of controls and associated actions that it can refer to during the autonomous execution phase, independently from the configuration of the control station.

This work was carried on within the JOiINT LAB¹, which is a joint laboratory established between IIT² and Intellimech³, dedicated to applied research and technology transfer.

II. METHOD

LfD-based methods mainly consist of three phases: Demonstration, Learning, and Execution. During the first, the robot records all the information provided by the system and sensors. Then, in the learning phase, the algorithm extracts from the large amount of recorded data only the relevant information and encodes the robot's actions to make them generalizable during the execution phase (e.g., dynamic movement primitives (DMP) [7], Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) [6]).

However, in the specific case of a control station, the image processing module implemented in [3] is unable to detect the push-buttons involved in the task due to the small size of the operators and their close positioning. For this reason,

¹ Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy.

² Centro di Ricerca E. Piaggio e Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione, Università di Pisa, 56126 Pisa, Italy.

³ Giovenzana International B.V. – WTC Strawinskyalaan 1105, 1077 XX – Amsterdam, Netherlands.

⁴ Consorzio Intellimech, Via Stezzano, 87, 24126 Bergamo BG, Italy.

¹<https://www.jointlab.com/>

²<https://www.iit.it/>

³<https://www.intellimech.it/>

Fig. 2. During the programming phase (a), the user shows the robot how to perform the testing task, by guiding the robot manually. After the learning phase, the robot automatically executes the tasks (b) identifying the elements on the new control station, and generalizing the motion sequences previously learned.

in this work, the learning algorithm was pre-trained with a neural network capable of recognizing them during the product testing phase. Lets suppose to use a generic manipulator with n degrees of freedom (DoF) equipped with an ordinary gripper. In addition, a depth camera frames the robot's workspace and provides both the RGB image and the corresponding point cloud to the learning system. During the demonstration phase, the neural network classifies and identifies the position of the operators in real time and sends it to an image processing module to obtain the clusters of individual elements present on the control station. At the same time, the user demonstrates the execution of the task for each operator presented on the control station and, as proposed in [3], s/he can divide the task into subtasks via a web interface. During the demonstration, the system records the Cartesian pose of the EE, the closing commands of the gripper, and the clusters received from the vision module. After the demonstration, as proposed in [3], the learning module identifies the nearest operator based on the minimum distance between EE and the centroid of the cluster and encodes the actions performed by the robot (Cartesian pose and grasping commands) using the DMP method. Finally, the cluster is saved in pcd format, while the parameters calculated thanks to the use of DMPs are saved in a yaml file. After programming, the robot is ready to perform the task autonomously. Firstly, the robot localizes known operators within the scene thanks to the neural network. Then, loads its data and the image processing module estimates the operator's pose. Finally an adapted version of the learned trajectory is instantiated at runtime and sent to the robot controller.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The method has been tested on robotic arm with 6 DoF (ABB GoFa CRB 1500) equipped with OnRobot gripper (2FG7). The experiments were performed with both a Realsense D415 camera and a industrial camera (ZIVID).

Figure 2(a) shows the demonstration phase. While the neural network identifies the operators in real time, the user manually guides the robot in performing the task, specifically

teaching it how to interact with the different operators. After a single demonstration, the robot is ready to execute the task independently. During the execution phase (Fig. 2(b)), a conveyor randomly positions a new control station in the robot's workspace, which identifies all the operators and generalizes the associated movements to their new positions.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a learning framework to program a robotic system in intuitive way for a product testing application. In addition, the method has been tested in collaboration with our partner Giovenzana as shown in the video attached⁴.

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⁴https://www.dropbox.com/s/ev8n3vf2d1wwn6/giovenzana_completo_fast.mp4?dl=0

⁵<https://www.jointlab.com/>